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Abstract

This report details the advancements made in Task 3.1, specifically within the Deliverable D3.1, focusing on the enhancement of interoperability between clinical trial databases and Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) for oncology. The Molecular tumour Board Portal (MTBP) and TrialMatchAI are central to our efforts, automating the integration and interpretation of diverse molecular and clinical data to support precision cancer medicine across European cancer centers. MTBP, developed at Karolinska Institutet, streamlines the capture and analysis of next-generation sequencing data, linking functional genomic alterations with clinical outcomes and trial opportunities. Complementarily, TrialMatchAI leverages state-of-the-art artificial intelligence, particularly large language models, to automate the matching of patient profiles with clinical trials, focusing on genomic biomarkers and other relevant patient data to generate tailored clinical trial recommendations. This system not only increases the efficiency of patient-trial matching but also enhances the precision of treatment decisions. APIs ensure seamless data flow and integration with CDSS, aiming to significantly impact the landscape of cancer treatment and research by providing a robust framework for data-driven orientation of patients to clinical trials.

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Statement of originality

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the context of cancer research, integrating diverse data sources and modalities is increasingly critical, driven by advances in artificial intelligence and a growing recognition of the complexity of cancer biology as well as the importance of high-throughput diagnostic assays in the clinical setting. Task 3.1 under Deliverable D3.1 focuses on these integration challenges, specifically aiming to enhance the interconnection between clinical trial databases and Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) to streamline patient care from diagnosis to orientation to clinical trials.

Task 3.1 develops a data model that captures the complexity of new clinical trial designs as well as the intricacies of molecular markers used as inclusion/exclusion criteria to facilitate streamlined integration with bioinformatic pipelines, such as those used in CDSS. This task addresses significant issues such as the lack of standardization in data formats, metadata models, and data access procedures that often hinder effective data analyses. As a proof-of-concept, interoperability of a clinical trial database based on that model and the Molecular tumour Board Portal (MTBP), an academic CDSS used across several European cancer centers, was addressed in order to demonstrate how molecular biomarker-driven trial information can be accurately integrated into clinical workflows, facilitating enhanced decision-making processes.

To further address these challenges, in this demonstrator we present TrialMatchAI, an AI-driven tool that leverages large language models to automate the matching of patient profiles with appropriate clinical trials. This system utilizes the approach for splitting criteria for inclusion/exclusion in clinical trials elaborated by ECRIN to parse and analyze clinical data and trial eligibility criteria, yielding structured data for both patients and trials in order to produce a ranked list of trial options for patients based on their unique genomic and clinical profiles.

The collaboration among multiple partners, including CNRS, KI, UiO, VHIO, and NKI, has been central to leverage artificial intelligence and include genomic data as a major matching criterion. This framework not only serves the immediate needs of the Molecular tumour Board Portal and TrialMatchAI, but also provides a scalable model for future cancer mission projects, ensuring that the progress made here can be exploited by the wider research community to improve cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment trajectories.

1 Introduction

In the context of cancer data management, Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) play a central role in integrating complex data streams to enhance diagnostic accuracy and therapeutic decision-making. This report outlines the progress and innovations made in Task 3.1 as part of the Deliverable D3.1, which focuses on enabling the seamless interconnection between clinical trial databases and CDSS. This task is part of a broader effort to develop a biomarker-driven clinical trials repository that remains current and is curated directly through CDSS, and to accelerate the allocation of patients based on both clinical and biomarker data.

Molecular tumour Board Portal (MTBP), automates a common process for the capture, interpretation and reporting of next-generation sequencing data which has been instrumental in the Cancer Core Europe group of hospitals. Task 3.1 has been crucial in developing the necessary procedures to ensure a robust data exchange between the MTBP and the clinical trials databases, enabling an environment where multi-dimensional, biomarker-driven clinical trials information can be integrated efficiently into clinical workflows. We specifically report on a demonstrator of MTBP's enhanced interoperability capabilities to integrate biomarker data types under a novel data schema relevant for patient cohorts, underscoring the CDSS's evolving capability to support complex decision-making processes in real-time.

This integration is further supported by our collaboration with the ECRIN Clinical Research Metadata Repository (crMDR), which elaborated an approach for splitting exclusion/inclusion criteria in clinical trials, facilitating our work on matching patients' profiles with clinical trials. Our matching tool - TrialMatchAI - leverages artificial intelligence technologies, specifically large language models (LLMs), to parse and analyze clinical data and trial eligibility criteria. This allows for an automated matching process between patient profiles and clinical trials, based on genomic biomarkers and other relevant patient data. The system processes this information to generate a ranked list of trials tailored to the individual characteristics of each patient, enhancing the precision and efficiency of patient-trial matching. This task involved a collaboration effort among multiple partners, including CNRS, UiO, VHIO, and NKI, each contributing their knowledge ranging from artificial intelligence to genomic data handling.

2 Molecular Tumour Board Portal

2.1 The Molecular Tumour Board Portal (MTBP) as a clinical decision support system

The Molecular Tumour Board Portal (MTBP) is an academic system developed at Karolinska Institutet that automates the interpretation and reporting of high-throughput molecular assay results for precision oncology^{1,2}. In detail, the MTBP annotates and classifies the functional relevance of molecular alterations according to distinct sources of evidence, e.g. whether a given genomic alteration is estimated to contribute to the tumorigenic phenotypes of a given individual tumour. In addition, the MTBP performs the mapping of those alterations estimated as functionally relevant with clinical actions of interest, such as cancer biomarkers of drug response, prognosis and diagnostic, according to distinct levels of actionability. Of note, one of the MTBP features is to match patients with clinical trial opportunities, as required in the advanced cancer setting. The MTBP is employed in several European cancer centers and considered as a medical device according to the new EU IVDR/MD regulation.

2.2 The Molecular Clinical Trial Match (MCTM) system

The Molecular Clinical Trial Match (MCTM) system is aimed to support an automated matching between high-throughput molecular assay results and clinical trial opportunities. Details on the MCTM system are explained in the deliverable D3.4; briefly, the MCTM provides a curation interface to gather information of biomarker-based trials according to a data model that is designed to enable this task (see next section). Of note, the MCTM is focused on capturing the complexity of the molecular criteria employed as trials' eligibility criteria, under the premise that this information is not always available/up-to-date in public clinical trial registries with the accuracy required in a prospective decision making setting.

2.3 Interoperability between the MCTM and clinical decision support systems

2.3.1 The MCTM data model

The MCTM employs two (password-protected) SQL relational databases, each housed in its own Docker container. These databases store user authentication data and clinical trial information, respectively. The user authentication data resides in a PostgreSQL database, which is accessed and formatted by the Keycloak system, which is used to manage the access to the data stored in a given MCTM database. On the other hand, the clinical trial information is stored in a MariaDB MySQL database, designed -as stated previously- to (i) capture the complexity of molecular eligibility criteria; and (ii) facilitate an streamlined integration with bioinformatic pipelines (e.g. clinical decision support systems).

Briefly, clinical trial information is organized hierarchically across multiple tables. One hierarchy is devoted to gathering the information on molecular entities, which is a key element in the MCTM system; a separate table model is used for the following molecular entities (at the moment of this document writing): single nucleotide variants and small insertions/deletions, copy number alterations, gene fusions, mutational signatures, gene expression and protein abundance, respectively. Each molecular criterion can be combined to

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41591-020-0969-2>

² <https://www.nature.com/articles/s43018-022-00332-x>

be based on 'AND' and 'OR' logics, including the use of 'absence' or 'presence' attributes that allow defining complex inclusion and/or exclusion criteria as appropriate. These criteria are part of the trial arm -level hierarchy, which also contemplates other (non-molecular) inclusion/exclusion requisites of the arm; among those, at the moment of writing this document, are those related with the age, diagnoses and previous treatments. Finally, treatment arm(s) can be aggregated to constitute clinical trial-level information, which also includes other descriptive information (e.g. type of trial design). Foreign Keys establish relationships between these tables, ensuring data integrity and relational coherence. In addition, any entry within each table always possesses a unique identifier and a creation timestamp that enables efficient data tracking and traceability management.

Of note, clinical trial information is gathered in a given MCTM database by using controlled vocabulary when possible. The MCTM system accommodates the use of any system, whose details are contemplated as part of the metadata of that database. For the MCTM database created as part of this project (see D3.4), gene names are defined using HUGO symbols; genomic variants are defined using HGVS nomenclature; cancer types are defined using the OncoTree taxonomy; and treatments are defined using HemOnc.org terms.

2.3.2 The MCTM data access

The information gathered in a given MCTM database can be browsed via a web application. However, the MCTM also possesses an application programming interface (API) that facilitates the integration with bioinformatic pipelines. The API is hosted on its own Docker Container and utilizes an open-source Javascript library, Express.js, within a Node.js web application framework. All endpoints hosted by the API require that a Keycloak authorized token is successfully parsed to ensure the user has the required credentials to interact with the API.

There are several endpoints configured within the API which allow for the database content to be queried according to different user requirements (e.g. to query for all open trials contemplating a certain gene as inclusion criteria). Every API endpoint returns a JSON object that qualifies the "status" of the response and, if successful, the result of the query. To ensure clarity and ease of use, the API documentation is routinely updated in the Swagger documentation available to MCTM users.

2.3.3 Integration between the MCTM and the MTBP systems

As a proof-of-concept of the interoperability between the MCTM with clinical decision support systems, we have integrated the MCTM with the bioinformatic pipelines of the MTBP. Briefly, the MTBP employs the aforementioned MCTM API to query its content; to implement the process of matching, the MTBP only uses (at the time of writing this document) the requisites on the molecular profiles and the patient diagnosis (i.e. the cancer type), as additional information (such as details on patient's previous treatments) is not usually available for the MTBP system. Of note, the MCTM states the type of entry for each individual molecular criterion that is returned via the API to facilitate the parsing of the content; for instance, in the case of mutations, the MCTM organizes the given criterion in: (a) a specific gene mutation in protein and/or cDNA coordinates, to be matched with the results of the corresponding NGS assay after ensuring the use of the same representation system as provided by the MCTM database entry (e.g. using the same gene transcript); (b) a 'regional' statement (such as 'inframe deletions in EGFR exon X'), to be matched after implementing the mapping of the corresponding terms provided by the MCTM database; and (c) a

'functional' statement (such as FGFR3 oncogenic mutations'), to be matched based on the functional interpretation provided by the MTBP analytical pipeline. Overall, the results of using the MCTM database curated in D3.4 to analyze sequencing data of a cohort of tumours by using the MTBP will be provided as part of the corresponding use case of the present project.

3 ECRIN clinical research Metadata Repository and categorisation of inclusion/exclusion criteria

3.1 ECRIN Metadata-Schema

Researchers are increasingly making data objects generated by clinical research activity available to others with the objective of enhancing the fairness of clinical research data. However, these objects are often dispersed across a multitude of locations/repositories and are accessible under a diverse range of conditions. Locating the various data objects associated with a study is a challenging endeavor, and once found, accessing them is also difficult, as many of these objects are only available under controlled access. The concept of a "metadata repository", which brings together all of this discovery, access and provenance, evolved out of these concerns.

The initial task was to create a metadata schema that focused on the required discoverability, access and provenance data points. This schema was first developed by ECRIN in 2016³, to support the development of a metadata repository for clinical study data objects, the crMDR (<https://newmdr.ecrin.org/>). This metadata schema has evolved into a combination of two schemas, one for studies and the other for the associated data objects⁴.

The study schema is based on a subset of the data points within the ClinicalTrials.gov trial registry (<https://clinicaltrials.gov/>), the largest trial registry in the world. This registry aligns with the core dataset mandated by the World Health Organization (WHO) and is also supported by 18 other internationally recognized trial registries. Trial registry data and that from ClinicalTrials.gov serve as the standard model for describing clinical research studies.

The data object schema follows the DataCite standard (version 3.1, <https://datacite.org/>), but with extensions to meet the specific needs of clinical researchers. This expanded schema includes additional details covering:

- The location, ownership, and access rules for data objects. Many of these objects are not readily or publicly available. Access usually requires an application, typically through the study's investigator or sponsor.
- Connections to the studies that generated the data objects. Besides journal articles, most clinical research data objects such as study protocols, statistical analysis plans, data management plans, informed consent forms, reports, website, and sample collections, are closely linked to the studies that created them. They're usually found by using the study name or unique identifiers, but this is not always the case, as was recently demonstrated for a link between studies in the crMDR and sample collections from these trials in the BBMRI catalogue (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/4-50>).

The necessity for two separate schemas arises from the fact that the relationship between studies and data objects in clinical research is many-to-many and not one-to-one. In order to accommodate this, it is necessary to store study details and data object details separately, with a separate 'link' table indicating which data objects are associated with which study. Each element has to have a reference to the other element type – a study record has one or more references to linked data object records, whilst a data object includes one or more references to 'parent' studies.

³ <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13063-016-1686-5>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/records/8368709>

The current schema contains 24 main data points related to studies and 26 main points for data objects. Many of these points are composite, consisting of 2 to 6 different attributes each.

3.2 ECRIN clinical research Metadata Repository (crMDR)

The crMDR is thus an openly available searchable database of all registered clinical studies (<https://newmdr.ecriin.org/About>), which includes links to the source registry pages, the results entries or results summary files, linked papers, protocols, data collection forms and a plethora of other related documents and data sets. For data sets, which are most often under controlled access, links to web pages with details of the application process for access will be available. The MDR can be searched for studies and objects by entering specific words or terms, or by using the relevant study identifiers. Searches can be refined by various filters, including study type, status, linked object type, phase, or start year. Search results can be exported as either JSON or CSV files.

Currently, the crMDR includes metadata records for about 900,000 clinical studies and, including all types of digital object (all registry entries, papers, documents and data sets, etc.), on 1.4 million digital objects. The crMDR aggregates and harmonises data from a dozen sources, mainly clinical trials registries (e.g., ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO ICTRP, EUCTR) plus bibliographical and specialist repositories (e.g., Pubmed, YODA, BioLINCC). It allows researchers and reviewers to identify studies related to a particular search term (e.g. a diagnosis, and/or study methodology, and/or location), and to view the materials (data objects) linked to those studies. The crMDR is updated regularly through the collection of data from the most important sources of information worldwide.

3.3 crMDR and categorisation of inclusion/exclusion criteria

Inclusion and exclusion criteria (IEC) define the characteristics that prospective subjects must have in order to be included in a study. These criteria are crucial for patient-trial matching, however, despite various efforts to create consistent systems for categorizing and structuring IEC, the level of standardization remains very low, with limited impact on current practices. Inconsistency persists because oversight bodies (e.g. ethics review committees) do not exert sufficient pressure on trialists to ensure that IECs are consistent and easily searchable, even though there are clear ethical reasons to make trial criteria Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). A promising approach to address these issues is to use Natural Language Processing (NLP) to extract structured information from IEC statements, thereby transforming them into machine-searchable data⁵.

However, using NLP for IEC extraction requires extensive training data to develop reliable algorithms⁶. The existing lack of standardization complicates this process, as IECs may be in different places (e.g. in a protocol or in a trial registration entry, both of which contain the IECs of a study) and be complex to interpret (e.g. where each statement starts and ends, which of the statements are criteria and which are headings, supplements, definitions, caveats and exceptions, how any numbering/bulleting scheme might identify criteria and sub-criteria, or even in some cases which criteria relate to inclusion and which relate to exclusion)⁷. Therefore, before applying semantic analysis (e.g. NLP) it is necessary to perform a preliminary clean-up step to identify the criteria and compile them as discrete statements rather than blocks of text.

⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC10148319/>

⁶ DOI: 10.1093/jamia/ocw176

⁷ DOI: 10.1007/s10238-022-00975-1

ECRIN undertook the task of attempting this clean-up step while revising the crMDR, and of making this training material available to the research community. This proved to be a significant challenge, given that the MDR contains data on approximately 900,000 studies, sourced from over 18 registries worldwide, with immense variability in how IECs are expressed.

Heuristic and text-processing methods allowed ECRIN to successfully extract about 80% of the IECs as discrete statements (in the other cases a statement would become over-fragmented, or not be fully separated from other, neighbouring criteria). That generated a database of about 9.5 million statements, each set of IEC being accompanied by an identifier for the study and a short study summary, as provided in the trial registry.

The database, along with the methods used to generate it, has been documented and shared with project members as a series of CSV files on a server managed by ECRIN, facilitating broader access for researchers interested in leveraging this structured IEC data.

4 TrialMatchAI: Advanced AI-powered Recommendation System for Matching Cancer Patients to Clinical Trials

In the rapidly evolving field of cancer treatment, there is a growing shift towards personalized medicine—a customized approach accommodating each patient's distinct genetic and clinical characteristics. At the heart of this transformation are precision clinical trials and in particular, those that utilize patients' unique genomic profiles, among other tumour specifics, to determine the most effective and safe individual treatments. Trial-patient matching is crucial for the timely completion of trials and for optimizing the impact of new therapies and interventions. However, matching clinical trial eligibility criteria with individual patient profiles remains a significant challenge.

In many instances, multidisciplinary groups known as molecular tumour boards play a critical role in aligning cancer patients with appropriate molecularly targeted trials. The molecular tumour board reviews each patient's case, considering the specific type of cancer, disease stage, genetic mutations or biomarkers, prior treatments, and overall health. These boards often integrate the latest scientific research and advancements in molecular diagnostics to guide their decisions. However, manually matching patients to clinical trials faces numerous challenges, including the consumption of valuable time and resources and the risk of missing suitable trial candidates.

Some private companies, such as MassiveBio⁸ and Tempus⁹, have emerged as facilitators, offering services that use closed-source automated systems to match patients with clinical trials. However, these companies typically charge for access to their databases and services, which can represent a financial burden for either patients or hospitals. This cost barrier may limit the availability of these advanced tools to a broader audience, potentially exacerbating disparities in healthcare access.

To address these challenges, we have developed TrialMatchAI, an open-source AI-driven solution designed to enhance patient-trial matchmaking. Central to TrialMatchAI are state-of-the-art AI technologies centered on Large Language Models (LLMs)—sophisticated artificial intelligence systems adept at understanding and generating natural language that underlies the bulk of biomedical data with impressive precision. TrialMatchAI is designed as an assistant recommendation system for deployment in research and clinical settings and is interoperable with clinical decision support systems. Its goal is to streamline the decision-making process for patient allocation to trials. The following sections will report on its essential components and discuss the anticipated outcomes and benefits of implementing this technology. See figure 5 for a use-case scenario.

⁸ <https://massivebio.com/>

⁹ <https://www.tempus.com/oncology/clinical-trial-matching/>

4.1 Technical modules of TrialMatchAI

Figure 1. TrialMatchAI's Workflow.

TrialMatchAI features a modular data processing workflow capable of handling unstructured, semi-structured, and structured data inputs, including clinical notes, mutation reports, and blocks of eligibility criteria. It processes these inputs to produce a personalized, ranked list of clinical trials for each patient. In the following paragraphs, we will outline the successive modules that manage the data processing flow from initial ingestion to the final generation of this ranked list.

4.1.1 Data Loading and the Dedicated API

TrialMatchAI is designed to perform the matching for a given patient with clinical trials locally in a secure environment, ensuring that sensitive patient data is managed safely. In this context, the **Data Loader** module is an essential gateway for importing varied datasets from public and protected sources. It includes a RESTful API that is locally hosted, facilitating direct and secure interactions with clinical decision support systems. The current demonstrator showcases this for the Personal Cancer Genome Reporter (PCGR)¹⁰ case (see the dedicated section below) on the same local server. This configuration supports the efficient and secure data exchange, ensuring the information is current and directly relevant, thus promoting an integrated approach to patient-trial matching.

Importantly, however, to maintain accuracy and completeness, the Data Loader module periodically updates the clinical trials database to reflect new trials and modifications to existing ones. This consistent refreshment of the database ensures that the system remains updated, thereby improving the alignment of patients with the most appropriate clinical trials based on the latest available data.

4.1.2 Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing Clinical Trials

Although clinical trial descriptions convey helpful insights that aid in patient recruitment, the eligibility criteria section is the most critical information. Inclusion and exclusion criteria are

¹⁰ <https://academic.oup.com/bioinformatics/article/34/10/1778/4764004>

essential components of a study protocol, typically presented as separate text blocks or as a continuous text paragraph. To qualify for a study, participants must meet all inclusion criteria without meeting any exclusion criteria. These criteria are often directly copied from the study protocol into trial registries, such as ClinicalTrials.gov, which holds most of the global trial registry data and features a single free text of eligibility criteria that often contains two sub-headers: “Inclusion Criteria” and “Exclusion Criteria.” Other registries might provide separate fields for inclusion and exclusion, but the formatting and structure of these entries vary widely across trials.

Efforts to make eligibility criteria machine-readable aim to integrate with hospital systems for efficient trial participant identification (see review¹¹). Semantic analysis is crucial for accurate matching, and bulk analysis of eligibility criteria can obscure specifics needed for optimal patient-trial matching. Approaches like natural language processing (NLP) for keyword extraction, patient pre-screening for narrowing the search space, criteria standardization to ensure consistency across trials, and sophisticated query systems to query the criteria attempt to address these issues. However, an important first step is splitting eligibility criteria into discrete units, which enhances downstream solutions like NLP and querying based on semantic matching. Improving the precision of matching patients to trials and leading to better participant identification and more successful clinical trials.

ECRIN has implemented preprocessing methods for the clinical research MetaData Repository (crMDR) to split the eligibility criteria field into discrete inclusion-exclusion criteria (see section 3). Adhering to ECRIN's guidelines for text splitting presented in section 3.3. (i.e., chunking), TrialMatchAI incorporates a preprocessing pipeline that effectively separates a single block of inclusion and exclusion criteria into distinct, discrete criteria. This step is followed by conventional text cleaning, such as extra whitespace removal, deduplication, denoising, and case normalization.

Preprocessing Patient Data

Similar to clinical trial eligibility criteria, patient data—whether unstructured (such as clinical notes and electronic health records) or structured (like tabular data)—must undergo necessary preprocessing before it can be utilized in downstream language processing tasks. Unstructured free-text data, including clinical notes, are processed similarly to eligibility criteria texts. This process involves splitting the text into discrete information fragments, removing whitespace, deduplicating, denoising, and normalizing cases. These now semi-structured clinical notes are ready for the text parsing phase, where further structuring is achieved. Conversely, structured tabular patient data are scrutinized to identify columns containing relevant information for matching to clinical trials (refer to section 5, “Model Comparison” for details). The useful information includes primary general information, such as age, sex, cancer type, and stage, in addition to genetic mutations and other clinical indices (diseases, diagnosis, therapeutic procedures, medications, outcomes, and pregnancy status).

¹¹ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36602707/>

4.1.3 Text Parsing and Structuring

Figure 2. Named Entity Recognition for clinical text parsing

The successful matching of cancer patients to clinical trials depends on the accurate and practical interpretation of complex medical and scientific data in trial descriptions and patient records. However, the terminology employed in these documents often varies greatly, presenting substantial challenges in managing and parsing clinical texts. For instance, the inconsistent use of gene/protein symbols and names across trials, electronic health records, and research articles pose significant hurdles. This variability underscores the necessity for extracting and normalizing biomedical keywords of interest to facilitate contextual parsing of texts, ensuring precise data interpretation and effective utilization.

The TrialMatchAI system addresses these challenges with an AI-based text parsing module that utilizes domain-specific Bi-directional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) models like BioBERT¹², PubMedBERT¹³, and Bio-LM¹⁴, all fine-tuned on publicly available biomedical named entity recognition and normalization (Bio-NER) texts. These machine-learning language models, specifically designed for the biomedical domain, can understand and generate texts containing rich biomedical terminology. As detailed in the "Datasets for finetuning" section, the models can identify and extract crucial biomedical keywords, including patient demographics, mutational details, genes, diseases, medications, etc. Additionally, a biomedical entity normalization sub-module links these keywords to concept-unique IDs (CUIs) in knowledge bases, for instance, mapping 'atg7' to 'NCBIGene:10533' and 'arginine' to 'mesh: D001120'. This structuring of clinical trial eligibility criteria in TrialMatchAI focuses on converting unstructured free text into a machine-readable and efficiently queryable format using a database management system. Although standards like CDISC¹⁵ (including CDASH, SDTM, and ADaM) are widely used for data structuring and standardization of clinical trials, they were not employed here. This decision was made to prioritize the specific needs of TrialMatchAI's information retrieval functionality. Future plans include aligning with CDISC and ADaM standards to ensure broader compatibility and standardization, thereby enhancing interoperability and facilitating integration with other systems.

4.1.4 Building a Clinical Trials Database with Vector Embeddings

TrialMatchAI enhances the matching of clinical trials to patient profiles by implementing a hybrid database search system. This approach combines the strengths of keyword, full-text, and vector (semantic) search methodologies to forge a nuanced information retrieval system. By leveraging the distinct advantages of each method, this hybrid system effectively

¹² <https://hpc.nih.gov/apps/BioBERT.html>

¹³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2007.15779>

¹⁴ <https://aclanthology.org/2020.clinicalnlp-1.17/>

¹⁵ <https://www.cdisc.org/>

overcomes the limitations inherent in using any single search technique in isolation.

Figure 3. Schematic Representation of Vector Embedding

Initially, the system utilizes keyword-based search—employing keywords identified in earlier stages—to quickly filter the vast pool of available trials. While efficient, keyword search alone may not fully grasp the semantic relationships between terms or their deeper meanings within the text. To address this limitation, vector search (or semantic search) refines these initial results by delving into the semantic layers of the content, ensuring the outcomes are comprehensive and rich in contextual and semantic relevance.

Therefore, developing a vector database that concurrently transforms structured and unstructured clinical trial eligibility criteria and patient data into the same higher-dimensional vector space is essential. This transformation involves encoding each discrete element—whether a piece of information from the patient's profile or a trial's eligibility criterion—into a numerical vector with a fixed size within this space. Distance metrics, such as cosine similarity, are then employed to assess the relevance of each eligibility criterion to each element of patient information. The conversion of this data into vector form is facilitated using text-embedding models from the sentence-transformers¹⁶ library. These models are crucial for capturing the nuanced semantic relationships inherent in the eligibility criteria of clinical trials and patient data, ensuring a more precise matching process.

Figure 4. Schematic illustration of using vector embeddings to identify eligibility criteria semantically similar to patient information.

¹⁶ <https://www.sbert.net/>

Finally, we store structured and unstructured clinical trial information in their original and vectorized formats in a vector database. This clinical trial database houses two primary collections (both containing openly accessible information on clinical trials): one for eligibility criteria and another for general metadata. The general metadata include a trial's identifier, title, brief description, overall status, start date, completion date, study type, cancer condition, age and gender of potential participants. It's important to note that patient data to be matched to the trials is not stored in a database. Instead, patient data (accessible within the secure environment) are imported in their original form from a local directory. The tool generates a list of ranked clinical trial recommendations (see section 4.1.5), which are then saved in a separate local directory. This structured approach ensures that sensitive patient information is handled securely while allowing for efficient data processing and retrieval.

4.1.5 TrialMatchAI's recommendation engine

The Recommendation Engine is the zenith of the TrialMatchAI workflow, utilizing a multi-stage filtering and search strategy for efficient retrieval of relevant clinical trials. In this crucial workflow phase, we employ the LangChain¹⁷ library, which simplifies the creation of generative AI applications, to develop clinical trial retrievers with enhanced search specificity. The initial retriever takes in general patient data, including age, sex, cancer type, stage, and preferred geographical location, to select clinical trials that meet these essential and typically fixed requirements, making the search process more efficient.

The second stage employs the aforementioned hybrid search technique that operates at the level of individual eligibility criteria of the focused set of trials. These criteria are stored as separate documents, along with their vector embeddings in the database, while being connected through the trial ID to facilitate later aggregation. This stage features two retrieval strategies: a comprehensive keyword-based search (using the biomedical entities of interest) and a vector similarity search. The BM25 algorithm¹⁸ is mainly used for keyword-based searches, enhancing document relevance by matching keywords from the patient's data. Conversely, the vector similarity search leverages vectorized representations of individual criteria and patient information, using cosine similarity measures to capture deeper semantic relationships beyond mere keyword matches.

To refine the accuracy of these search results, a cross-encoder neural re-ranker re-assesses the hybrid search results, leading to a more precise matching process. The aggregation of criterion-level predictions then generates a trial-level score, considering the proportion of inclusion-to-exclusion criteria matching the patient's profile.

The culmination of this process is the creation of ranked clinical trials – a curated list of clinical trials, each ranked according to its relevance to the individual's profile. We plan to enhance these listings with summaries generated by open-source text-generation Large Language Models (LLMs), employing a Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) approach. These trial-level summaries provide clear, transparent explanations of each trial's relevance to the patient's condition, greatly aiding users in making informed decisions about potential clinical trial participation.

4.2 Data for Development and Validation

4.2.1 Clinical Trials Data from ClinicalTrials.Gov

TrialMatchAI imports and updates clinical trial textual eligibility criteria data from ClinicalTrials.gov¹⁹. This website is a comprehensive resource and database managed by the

¹⁷ <https://www.langchain.com/>

¹⁸ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1561/1500000019>

¹⁹ <https://clinicaltrials.gov/>

U.S. National Library of Medicine (NLM), part of the National Institutes of Health (NIH). It provides detailed information about clinical research studies from over 200 countries. The platform registers all completed, ongoing, and upcoming trials. The website facilitates public access to information about upcoming, ongoing, and completed clinical trials. It offers a wide range of details on each study, including its purpose, type, recruitment status, eligibility criteria, study locations, and point-of-contact information. Furthermore, ClinicalTrials.gov provides insights into the methodologies used in the studies, outcome measures, and, in many cases, results and publication details. The platform also provides an API for users, programmers, and technical users to access all posted information on study records data. Using this API, TrialMatchAI hosts a feature to periodically update the clinical trials database to include information about new trials and update existing trials in case of modifications by their organizers.

4.2.2 Synthetic and Real Patient Datasets

To develop and subsequently validate TrialMatchAI, we require both synthetic and real patient data. For the latter, we have been in the process of preparing and signing data transfer agreements between VHIO and NKI and CNRS/UBx.

Synthetic Dataset

The synthetic dataset includes concise patient descriptions generated by the advanced text-generation LLM, GPT-3.5 Turbo. This LLM can understand natural language and can produce patient narratives that adhere to specific formats as dictated by a set of provided examples. These examples are drawn from the MIMIC-IV clinical notes – a comprehensive collection of de-identified free-text clinical notes from the MIMIC-IV clinical database (<https://physionet.org/content/mimiciv/2.2/>)²⁰. The dataset includes explicitly de-identified ICU discharge summaries from approximately 150,000 patients, nearly 40,000 of whom have been treated for cancer at the Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center in Boston, MA, USA. We have therefore selected the notes of cancer patients, specifically those of colorectal cancer patients, to create exemplars for synthetic data generation. However, these notes still lack molecular data (such as genetic mutations); therefore, mutation reports from the AACR Project GENIE BPC CRC v2.0-public dataset were pseudo-randomly integrated into each patient's clinical note to enrich the dataset. A total of 15 exemplars were initially provided to the text-generating LLM (gpt-3.5-turbo²¹), enabling it to generate completely synthetic patient notes that seamlessly combine molecular and clinical data. To date, 100 synthetic patient profiles have been generated for the sole purpose of facilitating the development of TrialMatchAI. The synthetic patient data includes fields such as ID, age, sex, present condition, cancer type, cancer stage, cancer location, metastatic locations, past medical history, symptoms, medications, diagnosis, imaging results reports, molecular testing, and treatments.

Real Datasets (VHIO and NKI)

The first patient dataset (DTA signed and data transferred from VHIO to CNRS/UBx) is derived from the VHIO data science and molecular pre-screening program. Of 432 patients with metastatic colorectal cancer, 179 (41%) were enrolled in clinical trials, with a subset based on genomic biomarkers. All clinical data was manually extracted from medical records by an expert data curator and transferred to a REDCap case report form before extraction and sharing. Genomic data were generated at the local molecular lab and constitute an ISO-certified tumour next-generation sequencing (NGS) panel (~500 genes) covering relevant

²⁰ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41597-022-01899-x>

²¹ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/models>

cancer biomarkers. Clinical data was deidentified (pseudonymised) and included patient demographics, tumour histopathological characteristics, staging at diagnosis, metastasis location, medical procedures (such as surgery), details about systemic anti-cancer therapies (regimens, treatment intent, start and stop dates, response assessment), and clinical trials (NCT number, start and end dates). A data dictionary detailing each element (value sets, code systems) is available. Genomic files follow standard MAF format. The VHIO dataset is set to be an invaluable resource for validating TrialMatchAI, particularly since some patients have already been successfully matched to clinical trials, providing a "gold standard" for comparison.

The second dataset (DTA still under legal examination at CNRS/UBx) will be provided by the Netherlands Cancer Institute (NKI) to further validate TrialMatchAI. The dataset is part of the Whole genome sequencing Implementation in the standard Diagnostics for Every cancer patient (WIDE²²) project, which investigated the feasibility and impact of Whole Genome Sequencing (WGS)-based diagnostics in routine clinical practice. WIDE was designed as an observational diagnostic consecutive cohort study to be executed at the NKI, including up to 1200 cancer patients in 24 months. In this study, patients were included when there was (a suspicion of) metastatic disease without pre-selecting on tumour type. WGS was performed in parallel and independently of Standard of Case (SOC) diagnostics on the same biopsies taken as part of routine diagnostics. For participating in the WIDE study, patients consented to provide an additional blood sample to facilitate paired tumour-normal WGS and to share their genetic and clinical data for study purposes – in full compliance with applicable privacy regulations.

4.2.3 Datasets for Fine-tuning LLMs

One of the core components of TrialMatchAI is the data parser, which employs fine-tuned LLMs. In their base form, LLMs are pre-trained on vast amounts of texts covering a wide range of topics, thus giving them a broad understanding of language patterns and structures. For TrialMatchAI, these models undergo an additional layer of fine-tuning specifically tailored to parse and understand clinical trial data, including complex medical terminology and patient records. This specialization enables the data parser to accurately extract relevant details from diverse document types, such as research papers, trial protocols, and patient health records.

To fine-tune the LLMs (e.g., BioBERT) for tasks such as entity recognition and normalization, we consolidate five specialized and publicly available training sets, each covering distinct entity types. These sets include BC2GM²³ for genes and proteins, NCBI-disease²⁴ for disease entities, BC4CHEMD²⁵ for drugs and chemicals, and JNLPBA for proteins, cell types, DNA, and RNA. We also incorporate tmVar²⁶ for DNA mutations, protein mutations, and single nucleotide polymorphisms. Additionally, the MACCROBAT dataset enriches our training resources with 19 other biomedical entity classes, such as symptoms, diagnostic and therapeutic procedures, and laboratory values.

²² <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33167975/>

²³ <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/gb-2008-9-s2-s2>

²⁴ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/24393765/>

²⁵ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25810773/>

²⁶ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/research/bionlp/Tools/tmvar/>

4.4 Clinical Decision Support System Interoperability with TrialMatchAI

Matching patients to ongoing clinical trials can be an integral component of genomics-based informatics tools that support the clinical decision-making process of advanced cancers. At the University of Oslo, we have developed the Personal Cancer Genome Reporter (PCGR, <https://sigven.github.io/pcgr>), a stand-alone and comprehensive molecular decision support tool for cancer precision medicine. This section showcases how raw molecular data interpreted with PCGR can be used to query TrialMatchAI's API. This procedure will, in principle, provide users of PCGR with a ranked list of clinical trial opportunities for a given cancer case, where the ranks are primarily based on the level of match between the molecular aberration signature of the patient/tumour and inclusion/exclusion criteria of ongoing molecular-guided trials in cancer.

PCGR is a software tool that processes multiple data files produced by high-throughput sequencing pipelines of tumours, each encoding particular types of somatic aberrations acquired by a given sample (i.e., single nucleotide variants, insertion/deletions, copy number aberrations, etc). Next, based on a suite of functional annotation and variant classification routines, PCGR assembles multiple read-outs per case. Pending on the comprehensiveness of input data provided by the user, the following read-outs can be automatically calculated and reported by the tool:

- a) Gene aberrations (SNVs/InDels, copy number events) with likely oncogenic effect - as determined by SOPs/guidelines (VICC/ClinGen)²⁷
- b) Clinically actionable gene aberrations ((SNVs/InDels, copy number events) - as determined by SOPs/guidelines (ACMG/AMP)²⁸
- c) Microsatellite instability (MSI) status
- d) tumour mutational burden
- e) Mutational signature aetiologies (HRD deficiency, DNA repair deficiency etc.)
- f) Gene expression outliers

The read-outs listed in a) to f) are all provided in standardized formats whenever possible, using official nomenclature, identifiers, and classification systems. However, these data types must be expanded prior to querying TrialMatchAI's API. In particular, considering the nature of unstructured molecular data found in the textual eligibility criteria for clinical trials (i.e. as in clinicaltrials.gov), standardized PCGR read-outs (a and b, typically few per tumour) will be transformed prior to querying TrialMatchAI's API, ensuring that the same gene variants are exhaustively defined and represented in an information-rich manner that is more suitable for LLMs, e.g., "EGFR positive," "EGFR L858R", or "oncogenic EGFR mutation." Furthermore, inclusion criteria frequently list negative/wild-type status of key biomarkers (e.g., KRAS, ERBB2), which means that populating the API query with such markers could increase specificity. While the definition of 'negative' and 'positive' status may seem relatively well-defined for simple genomic biomarkers in various tumour types, it is noteworthy that this is not so straightforward for complex molecular biomarkers. For example, standards for the interpretation of homologous recombination deficiency or tumour mutational burden are currently not well established, meaning that caution should be exercised if these are listed as discriminatory elements in rankings issued by TrialMatchAI.

²⁷ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35101336/>

²⁸ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27993330/>

Figure 5. This schematic outlines the utilization of patient-specific molecular data via the Patient Cancer Genome Reporter (PCGR), interfaced with TrialMatchAI through a specialized API. The process commences with TrialMatchAI extracting and parsing clinical trial data (Step 1). These data are then transformed into vector embeddings using an embedding model (Step 2), followed by the creation of a database (Step 3) to facilitate the retrieval and semantic matching of trial criteria with patient data embeddings from PCGR (Steps 4 & 5). A neural reranker is employed to prioritize relevant criteria (Step 6), aggregated to score each trial's relevance to the patient (Step 7). The resulting output is a ranked list of clinical trials (Step 8). A text-generation LLM model then employs a Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) approach to generate trial-level summaries (Step 9). The RAG method re-integrates the patient's data with the retrieved eligibility criteria of each trial, instructing the LLM to produce summaries highlighting the trial's relevance to the patient's specific needs. Finally, the ranked list of trials and the summaries are relayed to the PCGR report to be displayed within its interactive user interface (UI).

We are aware that a limitation of the envisioned integration of PCGR and TrialMatchAI is the present lack of clinical data provided by PCGR, including demographic information, diagnosis, phenotypic features, and other clinical measurements (e.g., ECOG status, treatment history, types of metastatic lesions, etc.). Notably, PCGR is an interpretation engine targeting *molecular data*, with a very limited focus on the clinical data associated with a given case/patient; the primary tumour site is the only clinical characteristic considered during data analysis. This implies that the resulting list of ranked trials by TrialMatchAI are first and foremost biomarker-guided and will require further manual interrogation to filter the results according to clinical relevance. A possible future direction may involve the adoption of PhenoPackets²⁹ by PCGR, which can allow for a rich representation of the combination of clinical and genetic properties for each case and will thus permit more powerful queries toward the API provided by TrialMatchAI, and in effect a more precise identification and ranking of clinical trial opportunities.

²⁹ <https://phenopackets.org>

4.5 Code availability and deployment

TrialMatchAI is designed to prioritize accessibility and scalability, ensuring it is easily accessible to healthcare organizations and research institutions. The platform's source code will be hosted on GitHub (<https://github.com/cbib/TrialMatchAI>), a decision that streamlines easier access, enhances version control, and promotes collaboration among developers and users alike. Importantly, TrialMatchAI is designed to operate seamlessly in local, secure environments without needing an internet connection except for initial installation and the periodic updates of clinical trial databases. This capability is especially critical for healthcare institutions prioritizing data security and adhering to strict privacy regulations.

For deployment, TrialMatchAI will be initially available for download via git, enabling it to be implemented as a standalone tool. This method efficiently bundles the application and all its dependencies into a single, deployable unit, simplifying the installation and maintenance processes. In the near future, we will create a docker container for TrialMatchAI, which will facilitate easier deployment across different computing environments. This containerization will simplify the process of setting up and running TrialMatchAI, making it more accessible and reducing the potential for configuration errors. Alongside the core application, TrialMatchAI features a dedicated RESTful API. This API allows the tool to be executed locally, facilitating seamless data exchanges with Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS), currently integrating primarily with the PCGR. The API's functionality will enable TrialMatchAI to receive input patient data effectively and deliver results. This dual-deployment model—as a standalone application and as an API-driven service—ensures that TrialMatchAI remains flexible and adaptable to various operational environments. Additionally, after testing and validation, we plan to register TrialMatchAI with the EOESC EU Node³⁰ to further promote data accessibility, interoperability, and compliance with international standards for software management and sharing.

Finally, the metadata and descriptors of the underlying AI models will be deposited to the DOME registry (<https://registry.dome-ml.org/intro>) to ensure full transparency of the process and adhere to the [DOME recommendations](#).

³⁰ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

5 Model Comparison

In order to improve the inclusion of patients' clinical and molecular data into the clinical decision support systems employed in cases of multidisciplinary assessment by tumour boards and to facilitate a seamless match between the patient and the clinical trial, we have developed:

- 1) A comprehensive catalogue of eligibility criteria for matching patients to clinical trials (ECRIN), which has been instrumental in the development of the pre-processing module for TrialMatchAI.
- 2) A data model of the database, including molecular markers to be used for matching patients to clinical trials based on biomolecular data (KI. Data model A).
- 3) An NLP-based parsing of clinical trial information to automatically structure data for matching patients to trials (UBx. Data model B).

ECRIN applied its expertise in the field of clinical trials to conduct a comparison between the two models (Data model A and Data model B), with the objective of identifying potential gaps and errors, commonalities, and differences, and evaluate the possibility of merging or harmonizing these models in the future.

The manual schema analysis was structured to first identify general similarities and dissimilarities. It then examined similarities and differences that should be considered for unifying the data models, culminating in a conclusion and comparison with the ECRIN metadata schema created for the development of the crMDR.

5.1 Data Model A: KI - Molecular Clinical Trial Match Data Model

Data model that will be used in a tool (interface) that will facilitate the curation of in-house databases of clinical trials (from center or network) to facilitate patient allocation to trials. Their model is aimed only for trials contemplating molecular biomarkers, in order to facilitate automating the matching between NGS results and precision-medicine trial opportunities in the prospective clinical decision-making setting. This data model accommodates the complexity of clinical trials and the complexity of biomarkers. The MCTM curation interface supports an efficient and accurate curation of the data based on the data model (see D3.4).

This data model was developed to collect information for clinical trials to facilitate integration with bioinformatics pipelines. The model focuses on collecting molecular information in a way that allows accurate querying by clinical decision support systems (CDSS), which aim to automate the matching of tumour genomic profiles with clinical actions of interest. The data model addresses the complexity of molecular criteria (e.g. multi-gene biomarkers and biomarkers based on descriptive or functional criteria), as well as new assay designs (e.g. adaptive/multiple arms). This data model can be adopted by data curation interfaces and to adapt existing repositories where possible.

5.2 Data model B: CNRS/UBx - TrialMatchAI Data Model

An AI-powered clinical trial recommendation system for cancer patients called TrialMatchAI. Its main objective is to seamlessly process genomic and clinical profiles of cancer patients and use this information to identify and recommend clinical trials with eligibility criteria closely aligned to patient characteristics. TrialMatchAI is rather a pipeline that starts with raw

clinical texts (both at trial and patient level), returns highly structured data, and performs patient-trial matching based on semantic and syntactic similarity between patients' profiles and trial eligibility criteria.

TrialMatchAI employs advanced AI-driven NLP techniques, centered on large language models (LLMs), to improve clinical language understanding and data structuring. Specifically, on the molecular tumour dashboard side, it is responsible for receiving individual cancer patient data via a dedicated and secure RESTful API, and on the clinical trials side, it retrieves and periodically updates clinical trial information from ClinicalTrials.gov, focusing on molecularly targeted therapies. The tool also performs data pre-processing using rule-based methods, including the splitting of clinical trial free texts into discrete criteria following ECRIN guidelines. The tool leverages pre-trained LLMs to recognise and normalise a diverse set of biomedical entities of interest from pre-processed clinical texts. Finally, in the patient-trial matching phase, TrialMatchAI takes both unstructured and high-level structured patient and trial data, performs vector embeddings via LLMs, and implements semantic and syntactic information retrieval to provide ranked trial recommendations, relevance scores and explanations that help users understand results and make data-driven decisions.

5.3 Comparison of Data Model A and B

The two data models present some similarities: they notably both contain trial level information. Data models A and B have a table with clinical trial metadata (*Clinical Trial* in A, *Trial-Level Meta-Data* in B), which share some common fields (description: *description/detailed_description, phase*, etc.). Some of the common info between the data models is split in separate "Trial level information" tables in data model A whereas in data model B, everything is contained in the *Clinical Trial* table and its nested *Criterion-Level Meta-Data* and *Entity-Level Meta-Data* tables. Arms data is present in both data models, with arm level and criteria level information linked to the *Arms* table in data model A, while it is a sub-field of the "secondary" *study_plan* field in data model B's *Trial-Level Meta-Data* table, meaning in this case that the criteria level information is linked to clinical trials, not arms. Both data models contain criterion level information, though for data model A it is specifically molecular criteria, where data model B doesn't focus on a particular type of criteria. Inclusion/exclusion criteria appear in both data models, through the *eligibility_type* field in in data model B's *Criterion-Level Meta-Data* table, which specifies whether an extracted biomedical or clinical entity is part of inclusion or exclusion criteria, and via the *status* fields in the Criteria level information tables (*Mutations, Fusions, Copy Number Alteration, Mutational Signature*), which indicate the presence or absence of molecular information (mutation, fusion, etc.).

However, these data models also bear some dissimilarities: as a whole, data model A's schema is structured like a relational database, with clearly defined primary keys, foreign keys, and atomic fields (one value per field, not a list), while data model B's schema structure resembles more of a non-relational database, with primary keys not clearly defined, non-atomic fields (arrays), multiple data types for a single field, and arrays containing other table's data instead of foreign keys. This difference may stem from the different recommendation systems linked to each data model; a non-AI recommendation system for data model A, which would match user input (genomic profiles) with specific fields in the database to recommend clinical actions, and an AI-based recommendation system for data model B, which can work with more flexible data structures (e.g. *text* field in *Patient Clinical Information-Level Meta-Data*, described as "free unstructured text") to perform the matching between clinical/genomic profiles and clinical trials.

Furthermore, it should be worth mentioning that the first goal of the two projects using their respective data models is different. The end goal for both is to provide a recommendation

system to match genomic/clinical profiles (patient data) with clinical trials or actions. However, the first goal of data model A is to be used in a tool (interface) for the curation of in-house databases, meaning these two data models don't serve the exact same purpose.

Another difference between these two data models is the presence of patient data (e.g. such as contained in clinical patient records) in data model B, which is absent in data model A. As a matter of fact, since the recommendation system using data model B is AI-based, it needs patient data to validate the results of its trained TrialMatchAI. These patient-related tables specify the essential patient data fields necessary for TrialMatchAI to accurately recommend the best-matched trials (both for this validation phase and for the fields of the user interface). On the other hand, data model A contains information about users, but it appears to be used to store data of the users of the tool (interface), not patients. Nonetheless, after the validation phase of TrialMatchAI, both recommendation systems would only use the user input from the interface and the clinical trial-related data to recommend the most relevant clinical trials or clinical actions.

Both data models, as mentioned previously, each have a table with clinical trial metadata. Furthermore, they share a common field in their respective tables which can be used as an identifier for a single trial: the NCT number (*nctId* in A's *Clinical Trial* and *nct_id* in B's *Trial-Level Meta-Data*). This commonality can be leveraged to perform joined queries on both data models, to obtain complementary data from data model B for model A, and vice-versa. This could be used, for example, to get additional data to enhance the performance of TrialMatchAI, both at training and inference time (after the training). As data model A contains information about molecular criteria that is more detailed than in data model B, this could be a quite valuable addition to TrialMatchAI's dataset, so tempted that more detailed information is stored into the public clinical trials databases, which data model B uses, in which case incorporating the curated and highly detailed molecular-level data from model A would be very relevant. Though it should be noted that, while the NCT number seems like a required field for data model B (it is the only identifier field), that is clearly not the case in data model A, where the primary key of the *Clinical Trial* table is an internal, auto-incrementing ID, and the NCT number field (*nctId*) is marked as optional for a trial, if the value of the *instItId* field is present for this specific clinical trial. It is conditionally optional because not all trials have NCT IDs, but an entry for a clinical trial still requires an ID that is not the internal *trialsId*, whether it be *instItId*, *eudractId*, or *nctId*. Consequently, it is unclear how often the NCT number field will be empty or not, and therefore, if the query joining both data models using this identifier will yield enough results to be useful.

Ultimately, it may be possible to unify the two data models, but it would certainly be necessary to create a new schema or significantly rework one of the existing data models to take into account the needs of the other (data model).

The ECRIN Metadata schema was developed as a mechanism to facilitate the discovery of a wide range of data objects generated by clinical research activity, which are currently scattered across many different repositories. It was also developed to support the development of the metadata repository for clinical study data objects. There are some similarities between this schema and data models A and B. Both describe information about studies and trials using similar fields, such as study name, study identifier, start date, study type, and so on. However, the ECRIN metadata schema was designed for a different purpose than data models A and B. It does not include patient-level metadata, molecular data, or patient clinical information. Instead, it contains very detailed information on data objects associated with the studies and that are of great interest for clinical researchers, such as the DOI, or the data object class (text, dataset, software, etc.), and notably it contains fields that gather information about studies and objects inter-relationships. Thus, a direct comparison between the data models A and B and the ECRIN metadata schema is not meaningful.

However, the ultimate goal of increasing discoverability and access is common to these models, and as such they contribute to enhancing the FAIRness of clinical research.